

Activation of ZIC family genes in CNS metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

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We report here activation of a family of genes belonging to the ZIC family in brain metastasis in humans with breast cancer. Measurement of total transcription in primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer and CNS metastatic tumors from humans with breast cancer revealed transcriptional induction of ZIC1, ZIC2, ZIC4 and ZIC5 in metastasis to the brain. Proteomic analysis predicted interaction of ZIC1 with Sox, LHX and TBX family homeobox factors, with Neurod1 and Neurog1/2, with PAX3, PAX6, and PAX7, with NKX2-1 and NKX2-2, with brain gastrulation homeobox GBX2, with EN2, OTX2, GLIS1 and PITX2, with the cell survival regulator *CIDEA* as well as developmental signaling molecules Bmp4 and sonic hedgehog (SHH). *CIDEA* was a top silenced gene in CNS metastasis in humans with breast cancer. ZIC family genes have described developmental functions in the CNS.

References

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